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Executive Summary

The purpose of this work was to demonstrate the usage of artificial intelligence/machine learning for metagenomics analysis. More specifically, we aimed to implement an AI-based analysis toolkit for human papillomavirus sequence identification that will be further used to try to predict cancer development based on HPV status and other metatranscriptomes present in the specimen.

Datasets used for the study comprised the whole cancer genome atlas (TCGA, <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>) database, a well-known and validated public database and part of the Swedish cervical screening cohort as well as the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort.

In this deliverable, we describe several metagenomics pipelines such as the HPV-Meta and the microbial metagenome pipeline used to produce the input data for the Machine Learning model. We provide the description of the process of creating the Machine Learning software to analyse the data, the challenges, the analysis and results, as well as the future plan for the improvement of the HEAP AI-based software toolkit for metagenomics analysis.

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Background

Human papillomaviruses (HPVs) are a group of double-stranded DNA viruses which comprise up to 222 different types, with new types being continuously identified [1-4]. About 12 HPV types are nowadays classified as oncogenic, high-risk HPV genotypes, and persistent infection of these oncogenic HPV types is known to be a necessary cause of cervical cancer [5]. Furthermore, other cancers such as oropharyngeal, anal, penile, vaginal and vulvar carcinomas, have also been associated and are known to be caused by high-risk HPV types in the majority of their cases [6].

Why do people develop cancer when being infected with HPV and why do others not? Why is HPV persistent in some subjects while it is rapidly cleared out in others?

Considering the global aim set by the WHO towards the elimination of cervical cancer, it seems essential to understand the biology of human papillomavirus by performing metatranscriptomics analysis and testing AI tools to enhance the prediction of HPV-related cancer. The aim of the study was to develop a well-performing classifier to detect and classify genetic HPV sequences from metagenomics tissue data. The biological question is to develop a classifier to predict the development of cancer using genetic DNA metagenomics data and data from RNA-Seq. We focused on cervical cancer due to the available cohort (cervical cancer screening cohort from KI). In the first step, we developed a viral classifier because of two reasons. First of all, cervical cancer develops in nearly all cases based on HPV infection, which is why it was important to check how the classifier performs on the viral data. The second reason is that AI has already successfully been applied for viral detection so that the classifier could be developed based on the available resources [18].

To achieve those aims, the work was divided between KI and ICM. The data analysis was performed by KI. ICM implemented an AI-based toolkit for viral detection. The computational infrastructure for the calculations was provided by ICM and tested in CSC through the Hopsworks software platform.

HPV detection - “HPV-meta”

For training the AI-based analysis toolkit, the HPV status of the specimens must be given in advance. Although next-generation sequencing has been extensively used for viral detection, there is a lack of standardisation and quality guidelines when considering sequencing analysis [3]. Moreover, there is a higher risk of possible cross-contamination among specimens when compared to non-sequencing methods (due to the high throughput achieved when sequencing), and therefore, a robust pipeline with well-validated cut-offs must be used for viral detection and calling. In the present study, we aimed to first develop a well-validated, robust and open-source HPV pipeline, “HPV-meta” (<https://github.com/hpvcenter/HPV-meta>) to detect HPV transcripts in RNA sequencing data which could further provide information to operators and warn for possible HPV contamination. To achieve this aim, a well-known and validated public database, The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA, <https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>) was used for pipeline development and validation purposes. TCGA is a collaboration between the National Cancer Institute and the National Human Genome Research Institute and contains molecularly characterization of over 20,000 primary cancers and matched normal specimens spanning 33 cancer types (<https://www.cancer.gov/tcga>, accessed on 2021-08-10).

For this study, we downloaded all RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) datasets from the TCGA portal belonging to primary tumours (n=9,774), metastases (n=394), recurrent tumours (n=47) and solid normal tissues (n=693) to

develop and validate “HPV-meta”. By using the GDC transfer tool, we downloaded 10,908 bam files comprising around 90 terabytes of sequencing data. For each of the bam files, we downloaded the corresponding metadata, including the specimens and clinical data (sample type -primary tumour, control, metastasis-, ICD-10, tissue or organ of origin and primary diagnosis).

“HPV -meta” pipeline

“HPV-meta” performs several steps including quality trimming, human genome filtering, HPV detection, cut-off settlement and fasta sequence generation (Fig. 1). The fasta sequence is intended for users to inspect possible contamination. The pipeline and all the tools used for the data processing and analysis are openly accessible in the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/hpvcenter/HPV-meta>). For this study, the code was integrated onto the Spark and Hadoop environment but it can definitely be used in other environments as well.

Figure 1: “HPV-meta” pipeline for detecting HPV transcripts in RNA sequencing data.

Flowchart describing the pipeline steps included in "HPV-meta". The pipeline includes removal of human reads, sort and conversion to fq files (samtools v. 1.10), quality trimming (Trimmomatic v. 0.39 (<https://github.com/usadellab/Trimmomatic>),[11] extra trimming (needed for specific library preparation kits, e.g: removing 3bp of R2 from libraries prepared with the Smarter stranded total RNA-seq kit from Takara, USA) performed with Cutadapt v 3.3),[12] re-mapping to the human reference genome (double human cleaning using Nextgenmap v. 0.5.5),[13] filtering out of human reads, mapping non-human reads to an HPV protein database (Diamond v. 2.0.7),[14] coverage calculation and, if HPV positivity is present, a fasta file is generated by mapping the reads to HPV genome references and subjecting them to variant calling using GATK v. 4.2.3.0.[15] (Image created using <https://app.diagrams.net/> and Inkscape v. 1.1, <https://inkscape.org/>).

A detailed description of the different steps performed by "HPV-meta" is provided as follows:

Filtering human genome sequences:

A close look at the original bam files included in the TCGA database (n=10,908) revealed that all bam files were mapped to databases

containing a human reference genome as well as other viral sequences. HPV was included in some of those databases. Therefore, the “HPV-meta” pipeline starts by using pysam v. 0.16.1 (htslib/bcftools v. 1.10.2 and samtools v. 1.10) with a bed file containing human chromosomes and genomic regions to filter out the mapped human reads but not the viral sequences. Non-human reads remain in the newly created bam file (file_name_NH.bam), which is then sorted and converted to a fastq file (file_name_NH.fq.gz) using pysam.

Quality filtering and human re-filtering

To obtain high-quality non-human reads, “HPV-meta” uses Trimmomatic v. 0.39 (<https://github.com/usadellab/Trimmomatic>) [11]. Parameters for Trimmomatic are as follows: -SE -phred 33 -leading 3 -trailing 3, -slidingWindow:4:15 and -minlen:18.

In the case of the TCGA, none of the bam files belonged to samples subjected to library preparation kits that needed extra quality trimming steps. However, as library kits are expanding, the “HPV-meta” pipeline includes the step of “extra trimming”, using cutadapt version 3.3. As an example, when performing library preparations using the SMARTer® Stranded Total RNA-Seq Kit v2 - Pico Input Mammalian library preparation guide (Takara, US), it is required to trim/remove the first 3 nucleotides from every R2 read for the RNA sequencing fastq-files [12]. The operator can choose to use or omit this step.

High-quality reads are afterwards re-screened against the human reference genome version GRCh38 using Nextgenmap v. 0.5.5 [13]. The program is run under default settings, except for -i 0.95, -R 0.75 and -silent-clip. Reads that map to the human reference genome (if they align with more than 95% identity over 75% of their length to the human genome) are filtered out,

and the corresponding bam files with no human sequences are then sorted and converted to fastq files again (File_ID_non-human_quality.fq).

HPV detection and cut-offs

High-quality non-human reads are queried against all HPV protein sequences included in the PaVE database (Papillomavirus Episteme, <https://pave.niaid.nih.gov/>, accessed on 2021-08-17), including all protein sequences from HPV reference and non-reference genomes), using the open-source software Diamond v. 2.0.7 [14], using blastx with default parameters and `-top 1`.

The positivity of HPV is only considered if at least 10 reads are present for one HPV type and 690 bp of its genome are covered. The cut-off is based on previously validated cut-offs used for HPV detection on total nucleic acid extracted specimens (cut-off 750 bp, ~10% of the total genome) [7-9]. As the HPV genome comprises around 8000 bp and approximately 1000 of them are non-coding, the "HPV-meta" pipeline has reduced the number of bp to be covered (from 750 bp to 690 bp), in order to maintain a similar % of minimum coverage for positivity calling. The "HPV-meta" pipeline calculates the coverage for each sequencing file and reports the total coverage as well as the coverage for each HPV gene. HPV detection will only be reported for one HPV type per specimen. In the case of multiple HPV infections within a sample, the HPV type with the highest number of unique reads will be reported. In the case that 2 HPV types present the same number of unique reads, the type which presents a higher coverage is selected.

HPV fasta files

The “HPV-meta” pipeline generates a consensus fasta file for each HPV type classified as positive within a specimen. High-quality non-human reads fastq files (File_ID_non-human_quality.fq) are queried against a database of known HPV sequences including all HPV genomes officially established by the International HPV Reference Center (n = 222 officially established HPV types, <https://www.hpvcenter.se>, accessed on 2021-08-17), together with complete genome sequences from HPV types that are not officially established yet (n = 222, <https://pave.niaid.nih.gov>, accessed on 2021-08-17), using NextGenMap²⁴ under the same settings as described above. For each specimen, reads mapping to the HPV genotype previously detected with diamond is filtered for further analysis.

The resulting BAM files are then processed through quality control and left-aligned using The Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK) v. 4.2.3.0, LeftAlignIndels module. The HPV genomes are then genotyped by GATK HaplotypeCaller. SNP and indel calls are made and hard-filtered, following GATK Best Practices. All variant calls met the following conditions: QualbyDepth <2.0, FisherStrand >60.0, Root Mean Square Mapping Quality <40.0, Mapping Quality Rank Sum Test <-12.5 and Read Pos Rank Sum Test <-8.0 to avoid strand biases, inflation when there was deep coverage, false calls at the end of the reads and low-quality variant calls. Since the GATK Haplotype Caller uses the HPV reference sequences as a template and annotates mutations/indels on them, the actual coverage (at least five reads) for each consensus was saved as a bed file using covtobed v1.3.1 (<https://github.com/telatin/covtobed>). The bed file was used later to generate a fasta file using bedtools v. 2.30.0, in which the regions of the

genome not covered (<5 reads) were marked with “N”s (instead of having the reference nucleotides in not covered positions).

Analysis of sequence identity

It is well reported in the literature that for each HPV type, extensive sequence diversity is observed when analyzing HPV-positive samples. Around 84.5% of women infected with HPV isolates do carry unique HPV sequences within their cervical samples. With the generated fasta sequences, operators can for example compare the sequence identities obtained for one HPV type in one sample, with the rest of the sequences presenting the same HPV type but detected in other specimens. The present study includes an analysis of sequence identity for all HPVs that were present in at least 30 samples (HPV 16, 18 and 38).

It is important to note that 100% identity is not final proof of contamination, as different women may be infected with the same HPV type and identical sequence. However, isolates showing 100% nucleotide identity should be considered as “flagged” for the operator in order to have a closer look if needed.

“HPV -meta” results

A total of 10,908 bam files were downloaded from the TCGA database, corresponding to sequencing reads from primary tumours (n=9,774), metastases (n=394), recurrent tumours (n=47) and solid normal tissues (n=693), were subjected to HPV detection using the “HPV-meta” pipeline. Four sequencing files (all corresponding to primary tumours) could not be processed due to failure/corruption in the original bam files and therefore the analysis was made in 10,904 sequencing files (9,770 primary tumours, 394 metastases, 47 recurrent tumours and 693 solid normal tissues).

All bam files belonged to specimens located at 137 different organs, with breast (n=1,203), kidney (n=1,019), lung -upper lobe- (n=642), thyroid gland (n=564) and endometrium (n=561) being the organs presenting the most number of specimens.

HPV detection

The “HPV-meta” pipeline identified 488 HPV positive specimens among the 10,904 bam files (4.5%) according to pipeline cut-offs. Positivity of HPV was called if at least 10 unique reads were detected and 690 nucleotides (10% of the genome) were covered for one HPV type within a sample, as described in the Material and Methods section. A total of 25 different HPV types were detected among the studies included within the TCGA, with HPV 16 (261/488), HPV 18 (72/488) and 38 (41/488) being the types most commonly found (Table 1).

Table 1: HPV types detected in RNA sequencing data from TCGA using “HPV-meta”

HPV type	Tissue or organ of origin	Total positive samples
HPV16	Cervix uteri (171); Tonsil, NOS (30); Base of tongue, NOS (7); Tongue, NOS (6); Cerebrum (4); Overlapping lesion of lip, oral cavity and pharynx (4); Bladder, NOS (4); Larynx, NOS (3); Liver (3); Oropharynx, NOS (2); Endometrium (2); Breast, NOS (2); Prostate gland (2); Upper lobe, lung (2); Connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues of lower limb and hip (2); Hypopharynx, NOS (2); Hard palate (2); Lower lobe, lung (1); Lower gum (1); Mouth, NOS (1); Floor of mouth, NOS (1); Kidney, NOS (1); Pleura, NOS (1); Posterior wall of oropharynx (1); Sigmoid colon (1); Skin, NOS (1); Head of pancreas (1); Brain, NOS (1); Upper Gum (1); Gum, NOS (1)	261
HPV18	Cervix uteri (40); Kidney, NOS (6); Sigmoid colon (6); Bladder, NOS (4); Ovary (3); Cardia, NOS (2); Cecum (2); Colon, NOS (2); Ascending colon (1); Body of stomach (1); Descending colon (1); Gastric antrum (1); Liver (1); Rectum, NOS (1); Transverse colon (1)	72
HPV38	Endometrium (41)	41
HPV45	Cervix uteri (23); Endometrium (2); Liver (2); Lateral wall of bladder (1); Thyroid gland (1)	29
HPV33	Cervix uteri (9); Tonsil, NOS (3); Overlapping lesion of lip, oral cavity and pharynx (2); Tongue, NOS (2); Base of tongue, NOS (1); Floor of mouth, NOS (1)	18
HPV35	Cervix uteri (6); Liver (3); Base of tongue, NOS (2); Kidney, NOS (1); Tonsil, NOS (1)	13
HPV58	Cervix uteri (8); Cerebrum (1)	9
HPV52	Cervix uteri (8); Posterior wall of bladder (1)	9
HPV31	Cervix uteri (7)	7
HPV39	Cervix uteri (5)	5
HPV51	Cervix uteri (1); Kidney, NOS (1); Retroperitoneum (1)	3
HPV59	Cervix uteri (3)	3
HPV30	Cervix uteri (1); Upper lobe, lung (1)	2
HPV68	Cervix uteri (2)	2
HPV70	Cervix uteri (2)	2
HPV56	Cervix uteri (1); Lateral wall of bladder (1)	2
HPV73	Cervix uteri (2)	2
HPV2	Breast, NOS (1)	1
HPV69	Cervix uteri (1)	1
HPV-mSK041	Ovary (1)	1
HPV133	Corpus uteri (1)	1
HPV26	Cervix uteri (1)	1
HPV155	Brain, NOS (1)	1
HPV94	Kidney, NOS (1)	1
HPV6	Anterior wall of bladder (1)	1

HPV types detected in TCGA RNA sequencing files. The number in brackets corresponds to the number of specimens for each organ/tissue of origin

HPV detection validation

The results from HPV type detection obtained with the “HPV-meta” pipeline were compared to the HPV mapping hits present in the original bam files from the whole TCGA collection for validation purposes (as the database used in the alignment already contained sequences from most HPV types).

All HPV types detected by “HPV-meta” were confirmed within the specimens, except for 2 samples where the genotypes detected with both approaches did not agree. One specimen (the cervical primary tumour) showed HPV 52 in the original bam file while the “HPV-meta” revealed HPV 58. Further analysis of original bam files revealed the presence of both genotypes, with HPV 52 showing 23 reads and HPV 58 19 reads. The “HPV-meta” pipeline revealed the presence of HPV 52 (16 unique reads) and HPV 58 (16 unique reads) and HPV 58 was selected as the dominant HPV type due to higher coverage (690 nt). The other specimen (the ovarian primary tumour) showed HPV-mCG3 in the original bam file (15 reads) while the “HPV-meta” revealed the presence of HPV-mSK041 (21 reads, coverage 1,119 nt). All specimens classified as negative by the “HPV-meta” pipeline have also been reported negative in the TCGA studies.

HPV coverage

The “HPV-meta” pipeline provided HPV coverage for all HPV-positive specimens, revealing that HPV 16 showed the highest median coverage when detected in gum, upper gum, oropharynx, the base of tongue and tonsil specimens (6,870, 6,840, 6,625, 6,231 and 6,148 nt covered, respectively, which corresponds to 86.90 - 77.76% of total genome coverage) followed by HPV 6 detected in the anterior wall of the bladder

(6,162 nt covered, 77.06% of total genome coverage), when compared to other HPV types and locations.

Sequencing reads from a total of 22 organs/tissues of origin where HPV positivity was detected, showed less than 2,000 nt coverage (about <25% total genome coverage) for all HPV types detected at these locations: brain and cerebrum, liver, colon (including ascending, transverse, descending, sigmoid and unspecified), corpus uteri, mouth and floor of the mouth, posterior wall of the oropharynx, cecum, cardia, thyroid gland, skin, pleura and lower lobe of the lung, head of the pancreas, prostate gland, ovary and connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues of lower limb and hip.

Analysis of sequence identities

Analysis of sequence identity was performed for HPVs that were present in at least 30 samples (HPV 16, 18 and 38). Within the HPV 16 sequences, a total of 245/274 was aligned (29/274 sequences were excluded due to fasta generation failures) and 30,012 pairwise comparisons were done ($245 \times 245 / 2$). Up to 2078.5/30,012.5 comparisons showed 100% identity, translating into 6.93% sequences showing 100% identity to other HPV 16 sequences. The minimal identity detected among sequences was 94.59% (Fig. 2a).

A total of 32 HPV 38 sequences were analysed. The minimum identity detected among the HPV 38 sequences was 89.23%, and 100% identity was detected in 83.2% of total counts (852/1,024). Clear clusters with 100% identity were detected for this HPV type (Fig. 2b). For HPV 18, 52 sequences were analysed, comprising 2,704 pairwise comparisons (52×52), with 13.17% (356/2,704) showing 100% identity. Minimum identity was detected at 96.47% (Fig. 2c).

Figure 2: HPV pairwise comparison among HPV-positive specimens detected in TCGA.

The pairwise comparison was performed for HPV 16 positive RNA sequences in the TCGA database (a), for HPV 38 sequences (b) and for HPV 18 sequences (c). BLCA: Bladder Urothelial Carcinoma; BRCA: Breast Invasive Carcinoma; CESC: Cervical Squamous Cell Carcinoma and Endocervical Adenocarcinoma; COAD: Colon Adenocarcinoma; HNSC: Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma; KIRC: Kidney Renal Clear Cell Carcinoma; KIRP: Kidney Renal Papillary Cell Carcinoma; LGG: Brain Lower Grade Glioma; LIHC: Liver Hepatocellular Carcinoma; LUSC: Lung Squamous Cell Carcinoma; MESO: Mesothelioma; OV: Ovarian Serous Cystadenocarcinoma; PAAD: Pancreatic Adenocarcinoma; PRAD: Prostate Adenocarcinoma; READ: Rectum Adenocarcinoma; SARC: Sarcoma; SKCM: Skin Cutaneous Melanoma; STAD: Stomach Adenocarcinoma; UCEC: Uterine Corpus Endometrial Carcinoma. (Image created using Python v. 3.8.10 and Seaborn library v. 0.11.2, <https://seaborn.pydata.org/>).

The metatranscriptomes

In order to provide all possible metadata to the AI toolkit, the presence of other metatranscriptomes present in the specimen was investigated in a similar manner. All 10904 bam files from the TCGA database that had been

subjected to the “HPV-meta” pipeline, were subjected to taxonomy classification. For that, high-quality non-human reads (output obtained after removal of human reads and before diamond in Figure 1) were classified using Kraken2 v. 2.1.1 [10], which was run against a reference database containing all RefSeq bacterial and viral genomes (built-in December 2020) with a 0.1 confidence threshold. A cut-off of 10 classified unique reads was used to discriminate positive genera for bacteria and viruses, and results reported all genera which comprised more than 1% of total bacterial or viral reads, respectively.

For each sequencing specimen, bacterial and viral genera, the number of unique reads and total bacterial/viral percentage was annotated. The samples were then annotated. An example of bacterial results is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Bacterial genera detected in cervical tumours

*Blanks were always used in each sequencing run and used as negative controls to assure quality.

The metatranscriptome classification analysis is currently ongoing and the results will be used as input for the AI-based software toolkit.

AI-based software toolkit: Introduction

The recent quick development and production of omics data, which are large, complex and multidimensional, made conventional analysis no longer applicable. AI technologies are able to identify genetic patterns and correlations and also integrate phenotypic or radiologic- data into the omics datasets. AI has multiple applications in genetic data interpretation in oncology, often being used to predict the treatment response based on the genetic variants. An additional advantage of AI over other genetic variant detection algorithms is the possibility to integrate further data such as phenotypic, treatment response or risk factor or other omics data, such as RNA-Seq or proteomics. These data are or will be available for the KI cervical cancer cohort.

Although some cancers develop based on general risk factors, some tumours arise on the basis of specific risk factors. For example, cervical and urogenital cancers usually are preceded and triggered by the HPV infection. HPV is thought to be responsible for more than 90% of anal and cervical cancers, about 70% of vaginal and vulvar cancers, and more than 60% of penile cancers. In our work, we focused on cervical cancer as the data from the cervical screening cohort from Karolinska Institutet is available for analysis.

AI has shown an especially good utility in the analysis of the viral metagenome data. First of all, metagenome data are large and viruses contain short fragmented sequences that significantly increase processing

time. Moreover, algorithms based on the database alignment do not detect viral sequences well, as databases are not complete because many viruses are still unknown. Furthermore, nearly 30% of the viral sequences are non-coding sequences so databases based on the proteins may not be of use when performing transcriptomic analysis. Additionally, viruses often try to mimic the host sequences, making their detection even more difficult with standard algorithms, such as BLAST. Therefore new and efficient solutions, such as these based on AI, have been applied to detect viral sequences [18][24].

In this deliverable, we developed a viral detection classifier. The cancer classifier, which is not part of D9.2, will be constructed based on the pipeline for the viral classifier later on. In the TCGA database, the data regarding cancer status are available so that the label for the classifier may be easily changed. For the dataset from KI, additional information regarding RNA status (active virus replication) as well as lesion status (control, CIN1, CIN2, cancer), age of the patient and status of possible cancer development (longitudinal data), have been available as a prognostic factor to predict the development of cancer.

Figure 4. Workflow of the **Pipeline** used for analyses

Data preparation

Machine Learning requires numerical entry data. The nucleotide data are categorical data and must thus be converted into numerical data. For the data preparation a One Hot encoder, which is the most common encoding method for amino acids and nucleotides data, has been applied [25]. In this step, a binary column for each category is created and a matrix or array is returned. In “one-hot” encoded data, if a feature is represented in a column, it receives 1 and if it is not present in the column it receives 0 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. One Hot encoding for ACTG nucleotides

In the following step the matrix embedded data are inputted to the CNN and undergo training, testing and validation steps.

The datasets

The dataset used for pipeline validation (TCGA), comprising approximately 11.000 RNA sequencing files, was also made available for training and testing the AI toolkit. Moreover, metadata corresponding to the sequencing files was included, comprising patient characteristics, diagnosis, tumour type and other clinical features.

Furthermore, sequencing files from the Swedish cervical screening cohort corresponding to 602 cervical cancers and 528 controls (no lesion at the time of sampling) with patient metadata are also available for AI training and testing (Table 2) and can be included in further analyses.

Table 2: Swedish cervical screening cohort dataset useful for AI analysis

	CIN3+ cases	HPV DNA positive controls	HPV DNA negative controls

	HPV RNA positive	HPV RNA negative	HPV RNA positive	HPV RNA negative	HPV RNA positive	HPV RNA negative
Total N	345	257	107	209	4	208
Developing to HSIL/CIN2+ until end of 2021	NA	NA	11 (10.3%)	27 (12.9%)	0	0

Datasets used for pilot testing

Deep-learning-based algorithms are data-hungry (both in terms of the data volume and its quality). As a consequence, the delivery of suitable data is a well-known challenge [16]. It should be noted that other implementations for viral sequence detection that are described in the literature tend to rely at least partially on more synthetic/mock datasets for training (cf. [17], [18]). In the case presented herein, we have relied solely on real-life sequencing data.

For pilot testing, the TCGA database sequencing files, the “HPV-meta” results and corresponding metadata for each specimen were used. The whole dataset consisting of 10904 files was used for calculations. Sequencing files provided had already been filtered and only non-human quality reads were present in the files. Other metatranscriptomes were not included at this early stage.

Challenges arose due to an imbalance in the number of HPV-positive and negative samples. Only 4.5% of samples were HPV-positive as classified with “HPV-meta”. Such imbalances in the number of negative and positive samples are one of the reasons neural network training may become

derailed [19], and therefore selecting another subset and/or using sequencing files from the cervical screening cohort is a must. The latter will be done in the near future.

We used a balanced subset of the TCGA available data and limited the training instances only to samples biopsied from the endometrium as well as cervix uteri (most of them HPV positive). These were 159 HPV positive and 159 HPV negative chosen to use for the classifier and split into training, validation and test set in the proportion of 101: 29:29.

Another challenge arose due to the sample sizes. The size of available sequencing files varied, ranging from several MiBs to hundreds of MiBs. The sequences from the biggest files could have easily overwhelmed the sequences coming from the smaller files. To mitigate this, it was decided to use only the smaller files (< 35 MiBs in size) for training. However, it has to be noted that this variation is commonly found when sequencing human specimens. During the network training, all files were decompressed and read on demand. Thus, out-of-core training was implemented and our algorithms are in principle not limited by a given computing system's memory capacity.

Moving down to the level of individual files, it should be noted that each of them contains a large number of short sequences, coupled with additional sequencing metadata. To process this data, two network architectures were tested, as described in the following section.

Neural network architecture

First, we implemented a recurrent neural network (with LSTM cells). In this implementation, it was assumed that all of the subsequences form a coherent sequence. The enormous total length of the whole sequence

(sometimes in the range of hundreds of megabytes), would have made processing with the traditional neural network techniques impossible. Consequently, a recurrent architecture was used for training, to exploit its memory property. However, the training time has proven to be prohibitively large with the use of this technique.

This made us settle for more traditional training techniques. All subsequences from a given file were labelled according to the value of `diamond_positivity` metadata field. Thus, it was assumed that all short nucleotide strings in a given file are instances of the same class, either viral or non-viral.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was devised for calculations. This architecture was chosen due to its versatility. This neural-cortex-inspired development has proven to fare well when analysing two-dimensional image data [20], and was subsequently successfully used in a number of other scenarios, including the classification of legally-relevant texts [21], [22] or malware detection [23]. CNNs were also already employed in the area of viral sequence detection [24].

```
model_cnn = keras.models.Sequential([
    keras.layers.Input(shape=[SEQUENCE_LEN, 6]),
    keras.layers.Dropout(rate=DROPOUT),
    keras.layers.Masking(mask_value=padding_mask),
    keras.layers.Conv1D(128, 5, activation='relu'),
    keras.layers.SpatialDropout1D(rate=DROPOUT),
    keras.layers.MaxPool1D(5),
    keras.layers.Conv1D(128, 5, activation='relu'),
    keras.layers.SpatialDropout1D(rate=DROPOUT),
    keras.layers.MaxPool1D(5),
    keras.layers.Flatten(),
```

```
keras.layers.Dense(128, activation='relu'),
keras.layers.Dropout(rate=DROPOUT),
keras.layers.Dense(1, activation='sigmoid')
])
```

Listing 1. Code generating CNN-based viral classification network.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
dropout_6 (Dropout)	(None, 80, 6)	0
masking_3 (Masking)	(None, 80, 6)	0
conv1d_6 (Conv1D)	(None, 76, 128)	3968
spatial_dropout1d_6 (Spatial	(None, 76, 128)	0
max_pooling1d_6 (MaxPooling1	(None, 15, 128)	0
conv1d_7 (Conv1D)	(None, 11, 128)	82048
spatial_dropout1d_7 (Spatial	(None, 11, 128)	0
max_pooling1d_7 (MaxPooling1	(None, 2, 128)	0
flatten_3 (Flatten)	(None, 256)	0
dense_6 (Dense)	(None, 128)	32896
dropout_7 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_7 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129
=====		
Total params: 119,041		
Trainable params: 119,041		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Listing 2. CNN's summary.

Network's structure is presented in Listing 1. It contains more than 100 000 training parameters (Listing 2). Whilst dropout layers were included, in the training procedure presented herein this regularization method was in fact not used. The dropout rate was set to 0.

For training purposes, the subsequences were one-hot encoded, with additional symbols added for lack of data and padding. All the subsequences were padded to 80 symbols. Due to the padding, the masking layer was used as the CNN's first layer.

The training

Two computing systems were used on the various stages of work. Test runs were performed using ICM's rsys computing cluster. The production runs, whole dataset analysis, involved the Hopsworks installation available in the CSC. The former is a multi-GPU HPC system, especially well-suited for neural network development. Its six main nodes are equipped with Intel Xeon Gold 6252 CPU, 380 GiBs of RAM. There are four NVIDIA Tesla V100 32 GiB GPUs per node (though our experiences have shown that multi-GPU training was not necessarily feasible for the network presented herein). The system was chosen on the basis of the computational resources it offered, well-executed resource provisioning and its general stability. The former system is using Hopsworks for cluster management and job instrumentation. It is equipped with a P100 GPU. The complete dataset was processed using the CSC's infrastructure and the results obtained using that latter system are presented herein.

In general, good training metrics (accuracy, precision and recall) were reached with only a small number of epochs. This means that there is a significant amount of redundancy in the data, which can be exploited to

reduce the training time. Figure 3 can be consulted for the sample training profile achieved during the exploratory work on the dataset.

Figure 3. Loss and accuracy values for validation dataset obtained during training. The curves have been smoothed.

When training the model using the data selected from the dataset, the following parameters were used: learning rate = 0.002, epochs = 3, dropout = 0, batch size = 32. Those values were chosen on the basis of earlier experiments using the smaller subsets of the complete dataset. This training took about five days, with ca. 0.24 ms per step. Those calculations were quite heavy for the available CSC cluster and it was unable to sustain calculation speed if other jobs were run at the same time.

By the end of the third epoch 0.8 accuracy was achieved for the test set and 0.81 for the validation set. This does suggest that no overfitting was present. Precision results were, respectively, 0.73 and 0.74. The recall was, respectively, 0.99 and 1. F1 score is thus 0.84 (training set) and 0.85 (validation set).

Thus, it can be summarized that the training was successful and a well-performing classifier was developed. Near 90% F1-score confirms the

feasibility of using CNNs for neural network classification, even when using real-life data. It should be noted that while various hyperparameters were tested using the smaller number of files (i.e. dozens), an extensive evaluation of different hyperparameters in the case of dataset presented herein was not performed, thus it is possible that those results can be further improved.

Using the implementation

For repeatability, the random number generators used for dataset generation were set to a predeclared value. Reproducibility is facilitated with the use of Jupyter notebooks. In the Hopsworks system, the implementation has been made available in the `cnr.ipynb` file. The code can be run by following the instruction presented hereinafter (instructions are for interactive work using Jupyter Notebook with Python kernel). The notebook has been adapted to automatically use the special HDFS accessors available in Hopsworks.

1. Log in to Hopswork under <https://86.50.253.93:8181/hopsworks>
2. Click on the Projects>tcga

3. Click on Jupyter

4. Configure and start the Notebook server, click on the Jupyter lab

5. Select notebook cnn.ipynb

- Run the cells one by one
Extract positive and negative samples, divide the data into train, evaluation and test,
create the model

```
def extract_positive_and_negative_samples(metadata, num_of_positives, num_of_negatives):
    data = hops.pandas_helper.read_csv(metadata)
    positives = data[data["diamond_positivity"] == True][:num_of_positives]["sample"]
    negatives = data[data["diamond_positivity"] == False][:num_of_positives]["sample"]

    return positives, negatives

positives, negatives = extract_positive_and_negative_samples(f"{hdfs.project_path()}tcga_Training_Datasets/1000_metadata.csv", 50, 50)
positives = positives.to_list()
negatives = negatives.to_list()

positives_train, positives_eval_test = train_test_split(positives, test_size=20)
positives_eval, positives_test = train_test_split(positives_eval_test, test_size=0.5)

negatives_train, negatives_eval_test = train_test_split(negatives, test_size=20)
negatives_eval, negatives_test = train_test_split(negatives_eval_test, test_size=0.5)

train = positives_train + negatives_train
eval_ = positives_eval + negatives_eval
test = positives_test + negatives_test

train = shuffle(train, random_state=42)
eval_ = shuffle(eval_, random_state=42)
test = shuffle(test, random_state=42)

train = [ f"hdfs:///Projects/library/tsga_sample/" + name for name in train]
eval_ = [ f"hdfs:///Projects/library/tsga_sample/" + name for name in eval_]
test = [ f"hdfs:///Projects/library/tsga_sample/" + name for name in test]
```

7. Run CNN for 5 epochs

```
#checkpoint = tf.keras.callbacks.ModelCheckpoint(filepath="checkpoint", save_weights_only=True, monitor="val_accuracy", save_best_only=True)
model_cnn.fit(train_dataset, validation_data=eval_dataset, epochs=5)

Epoch 1/5
18499/Unknown - 1024s 55ms/step - loss: 0.5232 - accuracy: 0.7142
```

8. For evaluation/prediction use model_cnn.eval/model_cnn.predict methods.

9. Alternatively, Hopsworks' Jobs interface can be facilitated to run a job non-interactively. For this to work in a distributed environment, all the neural network calculations code has to be wrapped in a function that is subsequently called from hops.experiment.launch(...). The advantage is that the more advanced tools are then made available, like the Tensorboard. An example is shown in cnn.py file, which is made available on Hopsworks.

10. For this to work user has:

Choose Jobs tab, click on the New job

11. Define job name

Job definition ✕

Job name

Job name

12. To have GPU available, chose Spark as job type

Job definition ✕

Job name - test

Job type - Spark

Python Docker Spark Flink

Add file (.jar, .py or .ipynb)

13. Select an implementation that uses hops.experiment API (herein, a sample cnn.py file is chosen)

App file (.jar, .py or .ipynb) - cnn.py

Select...

14. Fill-in the details (choose Experiment as job type)

15. The job is now visible in job list, click the play button to run it

Further work directions

In the next steps we are planning to execute the following actions:

1. Training the network with other datasets including a more balanced dataset from the Swedish cervical screening cohort. There is a possibility of getting even better classification results as the data are more balanced;
2. Changing the classifier labels so that instead of viruses the CNN will be targeted to detect cancer;
3. Including additional information to predict the development of cancer in the HPV positive samples. This information regarding active viral replication is already available for the Swedish cervical screening cohort. We can also integrate more data e.g. phenotypic or proteomics and assess their impact in the prediction of cancer development.
4. Exploring the CNN's hyperparameters

5. Evaluating the feasibility of including the first step of data processing in the AI-based pipeline that until now has been performed externally, that is diamond BLAST to filter out human genetic sequences.

Conclusion

We have shown the feasibility of implementing a neural network-based classifier for the identification of viral sequence presence. The main challenges arose using real samples. While a more balanced dataset will be used by adding specimens from the Swedish cervical screening cohort, the nature of human samples (having different sizes) cannot be changed and further mechanisms will be used to mitigate the effect.

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